

Sensitive Data Interest Group Road Map, 2022

Document history

When	Who	What
2022-04-28, version 1.0	KS	Incorporated comments on 0.3 and published the document on Zenodo
2022-03-30, version 0.3	KS, BZ, Sensitive Data community	Incorporated the comments from community and shared at March community meeting for further comment
2022-03-09, version 0.2	IG co chairs	Shared first draft with community
2022-02-26, version 0.1	Kristal Spreadborough	Completed first draft and shared with IG co chairs.

Credit Framework

<https://casrai.org/credit/>

Kristal Spreadborough	Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing
Aleksandra Michalewicz	Writing – review & editing
Nichola Burton	Writing – review & editing
Kristan Kang	Writing – review & editing
Sensitive Data Interest Group Co-Chairs	Conceptualization
Sensitive Data Interest Group Community	Writing – review & editing
Biru Zhou	Writing – review & editing

Audience

This Roadmap has been written for an RDA specific audience. It is intended to state the 2022 aim of the Sensitive Data IG for its group members, and to provide a summary of activities for future members/the wider RDA community.

Introduction

This document outlines the Sensitive Data Interest Group road map for 2022. It is focused on the theme of “towards a common understanding of sensitive data”. The intent is that this document should be revisited at the beginning of 2023 to plan the roadmap for future work. This will ensure that the work of the Group continues to address the challenges and opportunities of sensitive data across states, regions, and countries.

At the time of writing, the Sensitive Data Interest Group has been active in the Research Data Alliance for 15 months. The [Interest Group Charter](#) provides a statement of aims for the IG. During this time, we have scoped interest and needs in the area of sensitive data with a specific focus on global challenges and opportunities. Recent work has begun to focus on key first steps needed to progress this work. One outcome of these recent discussions was the need to develop a concrete position statement and road map to guide the activities of the Group. This is the aim of the present document.

A brief history of the Sensitive Data Interest Group is provided on the [site Wiki](#). For a history of co chair membership see the [site Home Page](#). The Group met for the first time as a Birds of a Feather in November 2020 at [RDA16](#). Following this, an initial group of co-chairs began meeting regularly to formalize the group. The Group has participated in two subsequent plenaries, [RDA17](#) in April 2021, and [RDA18](#) in November 2021. During this time, the Group also launched regular [Community Meetings](#), beginning in September 2021, and successfully had the [Interest Group Charter](#) endorsed in December 2021.

Road Map

At a recent community meeting ([February 2022](#)), the community identified having a concrete road map as an important part of 1) progressing the work of the IG, and 2) cultivating engagement from the wider community. The road map for the next 12 months, shown in Figure 1, shows an overview of current and future work, and a timeline for 2022. This road map is guided by the three streams discussed in the [Sensitive Data IG session at RDA18](#).

1. Developing an understanding of the vocabularies used to describe sensitive data across regions. This stream is currently underway. This stream is viewed as essential for the work of streams two and three below to take place. For this reason, the first stream (henceforth referred to as Vocabularies work) forms the bulk of the roadmap presented in Figure 1 (using green boxes).
 - Vocabulary survey launched
 - Collect existing resources on sensitive data vocabularies, and crosswalk common definitions.
 - Review preliminary results at P19

- Develop Glossary of terms based on the survey and the crosswalk exercise
 - Journal article publication based on the work of Glossary of terms
 - Presentation on Glossary of terms at P20
2. Developing an understanding of the different levels, risks, and sensitivity of data across different regions. This stream represents future work (2023 and beyond). It is yet to be scoped with the community and only a high level mapping is provided in Figure 1 (purple and red boxes).
 - Tentative: Collections/environmental scan on existing (sensitive) data classifications: levels, risks and sensitivity
 - Tentative: RDA Sensitive Data IG output on this collection (format pending)
 3. Developing an understanding of how to assess and classify data for authentication and authorization governance. That is, what kinds of protocols and procedures are needed to govern access to data from a technical and governance perspective. This stream represents future work (2023 and beyond). It is yet to be scoped with the community and only a high level mapping is provided in Figure 1 (purple and red boxes).
 - Outputs to be scoped

An additional piece of work is included in the roadmap in Figure 1 which explicitly states the need to develop a road map, and which proposes publication of an IG prospectus to share the IG activities with a wider audience (yellow boxes).

Figure 1. Visualization of RDA Sensitive Data IG Road Map.